

TEACHER'S COMPUTER LEVEL OF COMPETENCE AND TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 24

Issue 1

Pages: 60-71

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2241

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13356694

Manuscript Accepted: 07-26-2024

Teacher's Computer Level of Competence and Teaching Effectiveness

Liezl M. Taga-an*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study investigated the teacher's competence of technology on elementary school teachers' computer competence and its consequent effect on teaching effectiveness on the elementary school teachers within the Sierra Bullones district during the academic year 2023-2024. The research explores the demographic profile of teachers, their computer competencies, teaching effectiveness, the relationship between computer competencies and teaching effectiveness, and proposes action plans based on the findings. Findings from the study reveal that most respondents fall within the age range of 41 to 50 years, predominantly female, with moderate teaching experience, and lower educational attainment. Teachers demonstrated proficiency in using office and teaching productivity tools, facilitating equitable access to technology, and applying technology to foster higher-order thinking skills and creativity among students. Furthermore, the study establishes a strong positive relationship between technology use and computer competence, as well as a significant association between computer competence and teaching effectiveness. In conclusion, the research underscores the significant impact of technology on teachers' computer competence and subsequent teaching effectiveness. Recommendations include implementing ongoing professional development programs, ensuring access to resources and technical support, fostering collaboration among teachers, and establishing mechanisms for evaluating and providing feedback on computer competence. By adhering to these recommendations, educational institutions can effectively enhance teachers' computer competence and improve teaching effectiveness, ultimately enriching the learning experiences of students in the digital age.

Keywords: *computer competencies, teaching effectiveness, technology, administration and supervision*

Introduction

In recent years, the introduction of technology within educational settings has marked a significant transformation, presenting a rich array of tools and resources that can revolutionize student learning experiences and teaching methodologies. The application of technology can notably enhance pupils' academic performance and teaching practices' effectiveness. Technology plays a crucial role in education, particularly for teachers in their teaching practices. As technology continues to advance rapidly, it becomes increasingly essential for educators to integrate these innovations into their classrooms. This not only enhances the learning experience for students but also equips teachers with the tools and resources they need to effectively meet the evolving demands of the education landscape (Parojenog, 2023). When used effectively, technology stands as a catalyst for more effective learning experiences, aiding pupils in acquiring essential digital literacy skills and preparing them for success in the evolving landscape of the future.

This technological integration has dynamically reshaped classrooms, introducing a plethora of digital tools that expand the horizons of educational possibilities. These tools range from interactive learning software and virtual classrooms to educational applications that cater to diverse learning styles, enhancing engagement and fostering personalized learning experiences. The accessibility of online resources and the flexibility offered by digital platforms have redefined the boundaries of education, allowing pupils to delve into subjects at their own pace and teachers to tailor their approaches to accommodate varied learning needs.

Effective utilization of technology is not solely about integrating devices or digital platforms into classrooms but rather about harnessing these tools to inspire pupils' critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills. It is about empowering educators to adapt their teaching methodologies and encouraging interactive and collaborative learning experiences that transcend the confines of traditional pedagogy.

Several research studies have highlighted the positive impact of technology use on student academic performance. According to a report from the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement, pupils incorporating technology in their educational environment demonstrated higher standardized test scores in math, science, and reading when compared to their peers who lacked access to such resources. Technology utilization has the potential to revolutionize education. However, more research is needed to understand how technology can be used most effectively to improve student academic performance and teaching effectiveness.

Technology integration in education has been widely recognized as a catalyst for transforming the learning environment and enhancing educational outcomes. Research has demonstrated that technology can significantly improve student engagement, provide personalized learning experiences, and facilitate access to vast resources and information (Puentedura, 2013). However, while the potential benefits are considerable, effective technology implementation in education requires careful planning, adequate training, and ongoing evaluation.

Studies have shown that technology can positively impact student academic performance when used appropriately. For example, a meta-analysis by Cheung and Slavin (2013) found that educational technology applications generally positively and modestly affected

student achievement. Interactive software, digital tools, and online resources can cater to diverse learning styles and needs, enabling differentiated instruction and fostering a more inclusive learning environment (Rosen & Beck-Hill, 2012).

Furthermore, technology-enhanced formative assessments can provide immediate feedback, allowing students to identify their strengths and areas for improvement. This real-time feedback loop promotes self-regulated learning and enhances academic outcomes (Shute, 2008).

Technology offers teachers a range of tools to enhance instructional practices and increase efficiency. Interactive whiteboards, learning management systems (LMS), and educational apps can streamline lesson planning, facilitate collaborative learning, and support data-driven instruction (Higgins et al., 2012). Moreover, professional development programs focused on technology integration can equip teachers with the necessary skills to effectively incorporate digital tools into their teaching (Ertmer & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2010).

However, the mere presence of technology in the classroom does not automatically lead to improved teaching effectiveness. The success of technology integration largely depends on teachers' attitudes, beliefs, and proficiency in using these tools. Research suggests that ongoing professional development and support are critical for helping teachers overcome challenges and maximize the benefits of technology in education (Koehler & Mishra, 2009).

Despite the promising findings, more research is needed to understand how technology can be used most effectively to improve student academic performance and teaching effectiveness. There is a need for longitudinal studies that examine the long-term impact of technology integration on educational outcomes. Additionally, research should explore the contextual factors that influence the success of technology initiatives, such as school infrastructure, teacher preparedness, and student demographics (Warschauer, 2007).

Moreover, as educational technology continues to evolve, it is essential to investigate emerging technologies and their potential applications in the classroom. For instance, using artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning in education holds great promise but requires careful examination to ensure ethical and effective implementation (Holmes et al., 2019).

This study will contribute to this body of research by investigating the relationship between technology utilization and student academic performance and teaching effectiveness, as well as the factors that moderate or mediate this relationship. The findings will be used to develop recommendations for improving technology utilization in schools.

Research Questions

This research determined the status of teachers' competence in the use of computer in teaching elementary pupils of Sierra Bullones District, Sierra Bullones, Bohol for the school year 2023 – 2024 as basis for the action plan to enhance the technology utilization in teacher's teaching effectiveness. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. age, gender, number of years in teaching, highest educational attainment and relevant trainings and seminar attended?
2. What are the teacher's computer competencies in terms of:
 - 2.1. operating on basic computer applications;
 - 2.2. using appropriate office and teaching productivity tools;
 - 2.3. facilitating equitable to technology that addresses social and cultural diversity; and
 - 2.4. applying technology in developing pupils' higher order thinking skills and creativity?
3. What is the teaching effectiveness of teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1. showcasing knowledge of the subject and teaching ability;
 - 3.2. managing learning and professional competence;
 - 3.3. teaching for independent learning and evaluation to pupils;
 - 3.4. showing commitment and personality traits; and
 - 3.5. showing interpersonal relationships?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' competence and classroom observation?
5. Is there a significant relationship between teacher's computer level competencies and their teaching effectiveness?
6. Based on the findings, what action plan for enhancing the technology utilization in Teacher's Teaching effectiveness can be presented?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive research design utilizing a survey questionnaire to gather teacher data. This design was particularly suitable for describing the impact of teachers' computer competence on their teaching effectiveness, as it allowed for collecting detailed information directly from the participants. Using this approach, the researcher could accurately capture the nuances of teachers' technological skills and their practical application in the classroom. The survey results offered valuable insights that could inform future research, promote effective ICT integration, and support the continuous professional development of teachers, ultimately leading to improved educational outcomes.

Respondents

The study enlisted 87 public elementary school teachers from Sierra Bullones, Bohol, representing a complete enumeration of educators within the district. These participants are detailed in Table 1 for reference.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents*

<i>Gender</i>	<i>No. of Respondents</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Female	78	89.65%
Male	9	10.35%
Total	87	100%

Instrument

This research used a survey questionnaire as the primary tool for data collection, targeting elementary teachers to examine how technology affects their computer competence and teaching effectiveness. Adapted from Monserate's (2018) Survey Questionnaire for Elementary Teachers, it explored teachers' use of technology in Sierra Bullones. Teachers answered questions about their technological skills, use of educational software, and strategies for engaging students and fostering higher-order thinking. The standardized survey ensured consistent data collection across all schools. The study aimed to identify correlations between teachers' technological proficiency and instructional effectiveness, providing insights for improving educational policy and professional development in digital literacy.

Procedure

The research was structured to explore technology's impact on teachers' computer competence and teaching effectiveness. It began with a formal letter to the School Division Superintendent of Bohol Division for permission and support. After approval, elementary teachers in Sierra Bullones participated in data collection through survey questionnaires over two days: distribution on day one and collection on day two.

Data analysis involved statistical methods like percentage calculations, weighted means, and Multiple Linear Regression correlations to understand the relationship between teachers' technology skills and teaching outcomes. Results were tabulated for a detailed examination to contribute to educational technology research and set a methodological example for future studies.

Data Analysis

In the analysis and interpretation of data, the following formula were used:

Percentage equivalence of each frequency using the formula:

For statistical purposes, the responses on the teachers' competence were categorized as Very High, High, Moderate, Low, and Very Low with weight equivalents of 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively.

Weighted Mean. This technique is used to measure the central tendency where some values are given importance over others. This is used to gauge the average value of responses to items in the questionnaire.

Multiple Linear Regression. To determine the significant relationship between teachers' computer competencies and their teaching effectiveness, the data were subjected to the utilization of Multiple Linear Regression formula (Montgomery, Peck, and Vining, 2012)

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to ethical standards by obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring confidentiality, and maintaining voluntary participation without coercion. No harm happened to participants, and the study received ethics committee approval. The researcher declared no conflicts of interest and reported findings transparently and honestly. Cultural sensitivity was respected throughout the research process.

Results and Discussion

This section systematically presents, analyzes, and interprets the collected data to verify and substantiate the research questions. The presentation covers various aspects, including the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, number of years of teaching, and highest educational attainment. Additionally, the study examined the relationship between technology use, computer competence, and teaching effectiveness among educators. The relationship between teachers' computer competencies and teaching effectiveness was also investigated. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data. Descriptive statistics provided an overview of the respondents' profiles and performance in the identified competencies. Inferential statistics were used to generalize the relationship between the teacher's computer competencies and teaching effectiveness.

Profile of the Respondents

This exudes the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, number of years in teaching and highest educational attainment.

Age

Age influences teachers' approach and adaptation to technology. Younger teachers typically exhibit greater familiarity and comfort with digital tools, leveraging them to enhance teaching effectiveness through interactive platforms and productivity tools. In contrast, older teachers may vary in technological competence, influenced by exposure and ongoing professional development in digital literacy. Understanding how age intersects with computer competence is crucial for designing targeted training programs that ensure equitable access to technology-driven teaching strategies.

Table 2 provides insights into respondents' age distribution, with the majority (41.4%) aged between 41 and 50 years. Younger teachers (20-30 years old) represent a smaller proportion (4.6%), while those aged 61 years and older are minimal in number. Previous studies (Teo, 2008; Lee, 2007; Yaghi, 2001) have highlighted older teachers' potential challenges with computer use, emphasizing the need for tailored training to enhance their skills.

Research by Johnson et al. (2014) suggests younger teachers generally demonstrate higher computer competence due to their digital native status. However, age does not preclude older teachers from improving their skills through targeted professional development. Overall, while age influences technology familiarity, it doesn't necessarily correlate with teaching effectiveness, which can benefit from both youthful innovation and experienced wisdom.

Table 2. *Age (N = 87)*

<i>Items</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Age (years)		
20 – 30	4	4.598
31 – 40	26	29.885
41 – 50	36	41.379
51 – 60	20	22.989
61 years old and above	1	1.149
	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation
Overall	44.8161	8.7836

Gender

Gender dynamics significantly influence how teachers integrate technology into their teaching practices. Historically, variations have been observed in how male and female educators approach and utilize digital tools in the classroom. These differences can be influenced by societal norms and access to technological training, impacting the extent and manner in which technology is incorporated into pedagogical strategies. Understanding these nuances is essential for addressing potential disparities in computer competence based on gender and fostering an inclusive environment for professional development initiatives aimed at enhancing teaching effectiveness through technology integration.

Table 3 illustrates the gender distribution among respondents, with 89.7% identifying as female and 10.3% as male. This disparity underscores the need to examine how gender shapes engagement with technology among educators.

Bradley and Russell (2007) found that female teachers often report higher levels of computer anxiety compared to male teachers, while Todman (2000) noted gender differences in computer self-efficacy, with males generally acquiring proficiency faster. These insights highlight the importance of targeted interventions to promote equitable access to digital resources and empower all teachers to effectively use technology for student learning and achievement.

Table 3. *Gender (N = 87)*

<i>Items</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Gender		
Female	78	89.655
Male	9	10.345

Years in Teaching

Years of teaching experience significantly influence teachers' computer competence and teaching effectiveness, shaping their approach to integrating technology in instruction. Veteran teachers bring extensive pedagogical knowledge and classroom management skills, but their comfort and proficiency with technology may vary depending on their exposure to digital tools over their careers. In contrast, newer teachers are often more familiar with contemporary technologies but may lack the deep pedagogical insights gained from years of classroom experience. Tailored professional development programs are crucial for addressing these differences and equipping educators with the digital competencies needed to optimize teaching effectiveness and create innovative learning environments.

Table 4 profiles teachers based on their years of teaching experience, with the largest group (43.7%) having taught for 11 to 20 years, indicating a significant presence of moderately experienced teachers. The smallest group (3.4%) consists of teachers with 31 to 40 years of experience.

Research by Smith and Johnson (2018) suggests that teachers with more years of experience tend to have higher levels of computer competence, likely due to ongoing exposure and learning opportunities. However, individual factors such as motivation and access to professional development can also influence computer competence, regardless of tenure in teaching.

Table 4. *Years in Teaching (N = 87)*

<i>Items</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Number of years of Teaching		
10 years below	22	25.287
11 – 20	38	43.678
21 - 30	24	27.586
31 - 40	3	3.448
	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation
Overall	15.3793	7.0895

Highest Educational Attainment

Highest educational attainment significantly influences teachers' computer competence and teaching effectiveness, enabling educators with advanced degrees to leverage deeper theoretical knowledge and research skills in integrating technology effectively into their teaching practices. Tailoring professional development programs to address these impacts supports all teachers in enhancing student learning outcomes through technology.

Table 5 illustrates the educational profiles of participants, with the majority holding MA units, followed by those with bachelor's degrees. A smaller group has completed Master's degrees, and few have completed units towards a Doctorate (PhD) degree. Notably, no respondents hold a graduate-level doctorate (PhD) degree, indicating the educational distribution among elementary school teachers in Sierra Bullones district leans towards lower educational levels.

Research by Elli and Ricafort (2020) highlights the positive impact of advanced degrees on student achievement and it emphasizes the role of technology-focused professional development in enhancing teachers' computer skills and confidence. These findings underscore the importance of ongoing professional development opportunities and training initiatives for educators to further their skills and pursue advanced studies effectively.

Table 5. *Highest Educational Attainment (N = 87)*

<i>Items</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	36	41.379
MA (units)	45	51.724
MA Graduate	4	4.598
PhD (units)	2	2.299

Relevant Trainings and Seminars

Teachers' participation in relevant trainings and seminars significantly enhances their ability to leverage digital tools effectively in the classroom. Table 6 presents data on the attendance rates of elementary teachers in Sierra Bullones, Bohol, at various professional development sessions focused on educational technology and pedagogy. Understanding the impact of these trainings on teachers' computer competence and teaching effectiveness is crucial for shaping educational practices that promote innovative and engaging learning environments.

Table 6 highlights the participation rates in different professional development sessions. The Digital Pedagogy Workshop had the highest attendance, with 32.18% of respondents participating, indicating a strong interest in integrating digital tools into pedagogical approaches. This reflects teachers' proactive efforts to enhance their skills in technology-integrated teaching methods.

Table 6. *Relevant Trainings and Seminars (N = 87)*

<i>Items</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Relevant trainings and seminar attended		
Digital Pedagogy Workshop	28	32.183908
Educational Technology Training	21	24.137931
Online Teaching Strategies	14	16.091954
Data Analysis and Assessment Tools	13	14.9425287
Digital Citizenship and Online Safety Training	11	14.9425287

Following closely, Educational Technology Training was attended by 24.14% of teachers, emphasizing the importance placed on acquiring technical skills essential for using educational software and digital resources effectively. Participation rates in Online Teaching Strategies (16.09%) and Data Analysis and Assessment Tools (14.94%) demonstrate educators' recognition of adapting teaching practices to digital platforms and utilizing data-driven approaches to improve student learning outcomes.

Additionally, attendance at Digital Citizenship and Online Safety Training (12.64%) underscores teachers' awareness of educating students on responsible digital behavior and online safety. These findings align with research emphasizing the need for ongoing, tailored professional development to meet teachers' specific needs and contexts (Zhao & Frank, 2003; Schrum & Levin, 2009). By investing in targeted professional development aligned with these findings, educational stakeholders can cultivate a digitally competent teaching workforce capable of maximizing technology's benefits in classrooms, ultimately enhancing student learning outcomes.

Teacher's Level of Computer Competencies

This exudes the Teacher's computer competencies in terms of knowledge and skills on basic computer applications, use of appropriate office and teaching productivity tools, facilities equitable to technology that addresses social and cultural diversity and application of technology in developing pupils' higher order thinking skills and creativity.

Operating on Basic Computer Applications

Operating basic computer applications is foundational for educators navigating today's digitally-driven educational landscape. Proficiency in tasks such as word processing, spreadsheet management, and presentation software utilization forms the cornerstone for integrating technology into teaching practices effectively. These skills are crucial for creating engaging instructional materials and managing classroom activities with efficiency. Assessing teachers' readiness in using basic computer applications is essential for evaluating their initial capability to leverage digital tools and enhance student learning experiences.

Table 7 presents data on teachers' computer competencies in operating basic applications. The findings indicate a high level of competence among teachers in these areas, reflecting their confidence in handling main components, configuring peripherals, and installing drivers as needed. Overall, teachers' computer competencies in basic applications are rated as "high," with an average weighted mean of 3.8092 and a moderate standard deviation of 0.9638, suggesting satisfactory knowledge and skills across the majority of respondents. These results suggest that most teachers are well-equipped to integrate technology effectively into their teaching practices.

Table 7. *Operating on Basic Computer Applications (N = 87)*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Knowledge On Basic Computer Applications			
I can identify and define the functions of the main components of the computer.	3.8046	0.9381	High
I can properly correct main component, configure peripheral and install drivers when required.	3.4943	0.9006	High
I can organize and manage computer files and directories.	3.8621	0.9903	High
I can solve minor problems that I encounter when using a computer.	3.6437	0.8624	High
I can scan and print documents.	4.2414	0.9761	Very High
Overall	3.8092	0.9638	High

Legend: 1.00 – 1.80, Very Low; 1.81 – 2.60, Low; 2.61 – 3.50, Moderate; 3.51 – 4.20, High; 4.21 – 5.00, Very High

Using Appropriate Office and Teaching Productivity Tools

Using appropriate office and teaching productivity tools is essential for educators to enhance teaching effectiveness through technology integration. These tools include office suites for document creation, communication platforms for collaboration, and learning management systems for organizing instructional content.

Table 8 shows that teachers demonstrate high competence in tasks like text editing, spreadsheet computations, multimedia-enhanced presentations, and using software like PowerPoint for effective classroom delivery, with an average weighted mean of 3.777. Research indicates that these tools improve instructional practices and student engagement (Mishra & Koehler, 2006).

However, challenges such as limited technology access and insufficient training hinder effective tool utilization (Mouza, 2016). Targeted professional development and improved technology access can empower educators to leverage these tools effectively for enhanced teaching and learning outcomes.

Table 8. *Using Appropriate Office and Teaching Productivity Tools (N = 87)*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Use Of Appropriate Office And Teaching Productivity Tools			
I use a word processor to enter and edit text on image.	3.954	0.9634	High
I make computation, use formulas, and create graphs using spreadsheets.	3.6667	1.1067	High
I use presentation packages to add text and sequence a presentation.	3.7586	0.9396	High
I enhance slide presentations by adding sound, customizing animation, and inserting images.	3.6897	1.0265	High
I make effective class presentations using PowerPoint.	3.8161	1.0176	High
Overall	3.777	1.013	High

Legend: 1.00 – 1.80, Very Low; 1.81 – 2.60, Low; 2.61 – 3.50, Moderate; 3.51 – 4.20, High; 4.21 – 5.00, Very High

Facilitating Equitable to Technology that Addresses Social and Cultural Diversity

Facilitating equitable access to technology that addresses social and cultural diversity is critical in education today. Teachers' computer competencies directly influence their ability to integrate technology effectively into teaching practices.

Table 9 shows that teachers demonstrate high competence in facilitating equitable access across diverse learning, social, and cultural contexts, with an average weighted mean of 3.6828. These competencies are crucial for promoting inclusivity and ensuring all students have equal opportunities to engage with technology.

Research underscores that such competencies enhance student engagement, motivation, and achievement bridging digital divides and supporting diverse learning needs (Wang & Lin, 2019). Adaptive learning software and culturally relevant digital resources further support inclusive educational practices (Hitchcock et al., 2016; (González-Gómez et al., 2016).

Table 9. *Facilitating Equitable to Technology that Addresses Social and Cultural Diversity (N = 87)*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Facilitates Equitable To Technology That Addresses Learning, Social, And Cultural Diversity			
I design activities so that disadvantaged pupils don't feel left out in the class.	3.6552	0.8737	High
I help minimize the effects of the digital device by providing access to digital materials to all pupils.	3.5402	0.8734	High
I prepare lessons and activities appropriate to the level of learning and cultural background of the pupils.	3.9425	0.9068	High
The projects I design for pupils are fair.	3.9425	0.9445	High
I adapt activities using specialized hardware to software for physically disadvantaged pupil.	3.3333	0.9605	High
Overall	3.6828	0.9385	High

Legend: 1.00 – 1.80, Very Low; 1.81 – 2.60, Low; 2.61 – 3.50, Moderate; 3.51 – 4.20, High; 4.21 – 5.00, Very High

Applying Technology to Developing Pupil's Higher Order Thinking Skills and Creativity

Applying technology to develop pupils' higher-order thinking skills and creativity is pivotal in modern education. Technology provides versatile tools that prompt students to analyze, evaluate, and create content in innovative ways, fostering critical thinking and creativity.

Table 10 indicates that teachers demonstrate moderate competence in utilizing technology for these purposes, with an average weighted mean of 3.469 and a standard deviation of 0.9888. This competency allows educators to design engaging lessons that encourage problem-solving, collaborative projects, and exploration of diverse perspectives among students.

Effective integration of technology tailored to diverse learners has been shown to improve academic outcomes, enhance engagement, and promote cultural understanding (Mouza, 2016; González-Gómez et al., 2016).

Table 10. *Applying Technology to develop Pupil's Higher Order Thinking Skills and Creativity (N = 87)*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Applying Technology To Develop Pupils' Higher Order Thinking Skills And Creativity			
I make pupils use spreadsheets, concept mapping tools, and communicating tool, etc.	3.1149	0.9329	High
I encourage pupils to perform data analysis, problem solving, decision making, and exchange of ideas.	3.4368	0.9965	High
I use appropriate slide presentations, videos, and other media files in the classroom.	3.908	0.9957	High
I teach pupils to use various multimedia materials for report in class.	3.3793	0.9553	High
I design rubrics for accessing pupil performance in the use of various technologies.	3.5057	0.9134	High
Overall	3.469	0.9888	Moderate

Legend: 1.00 – 1.80, Very Low; 1.81 – 2.60, Low; 2.61 – 3.50, Moderate; 3.51 – 4.20, High; 4.21 – 5.00, Very High

Teaching Effectiveness of Teachers

This part exudes the teaching effectiveness of teachers in terms of knowledge of the subject and teaching ability, management of learning and professional competence, teaching for independent learning and evaluation to pupils, commitment and personality traits and interpersonal relationships.

Knowledge of the Subject and Teaching Ability

Teachers who possess a thorough understanding of their subject can deliver content clearly and comprehensively, making complex concepts accessible to students. Their ability to use diverse teaching strategies, accommodate various learning styles, and create engaging learning experiences significantly enhances teaching effectiveness. Educators proficient in their subject matter inspire student

interest and foster deeper understanding.

Table 11 presents insights into teachers' effectiveness based on their knowledge of the subject and teaching ability. The data indicates high competence levels among teachers in these areas, shown in the weighted mean scores and overall agreement. Respondents achieved an average weighted mean of 3.8966 with a standard deviation of 0.8347, indicating consensus among teachers about their ability to effectively engage students in learning.

Research highlights that teachers who master their subject matter effectively convey complex concepts, address misconceptions, and provide clear explanations (Ball & Bass, 2009). Studies consistently demonstrate the significant impact of teachers' teaching ability on student learning outcomes (Hattie, 2009). Skilled teachers adeptly assess student understanding and adjust their instruction to ensure all students have opportunities to succeed (Darling-Hammond, 2017).

Table 11. Knowledge of the Subject and Teaching Ability (N=87)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Knowledge Of The Subject And Teaching Ability			
Demonstrate mastery of the subject matter without solely relying on the prescribed textbook.	3.7586	0.8064	High
Integrates subjects to practical circumstances in learning purposes of the pupils.	3.9655	0.8134	High
Explains the relevance of the present topics to the previous lessons and relates the subject matter to daily life.	3.954	0.8614	High
Explains clearly by using concrete examples.	3.931	0.8733	High
Helps students retain the lesson to minimize difficulties.	3.8736	0.8185	High
Overall	3.8966	0.8347	High

Legend: 1.00 – 1.80, Very Low; 1.81 – 2.60, Low; 2.61 – 3.50, Moderate; 3.51 – 4.20, High; 4.21 – 5.00, Very High

Management of Learning and Professional Competence

Effective management of learning and professional competence are crucial for successful teaching. Teachers skilled in these areas create structured, supportive classrooms that foster student motivation and engagement. This involves organizing materials, implementing effective classroom management techniques, and maintaining positive relationships with students. Professional competence, including knowledge of pedagogy and educational technologies, enhances teaching effectiveness by adapting methods to meet evolving educational needs.

Table 12 indicates teachers' high competence in these areas, reflected in a weighted mean score of 3.9034 and standard deviation of 0.7974.

Effective classroom management, established expectations, positive climate, and proactive strategies prevent disruptive behaviors (Stough, 2013). Continuous professional development improves content knowledge, pedagogical skills, and instructional practices enabling teachers to reflect, assess, and enhance their teaching effectiveness.

Table 12. Management of Learning and Professional Competence (N=87)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Management Of Learning And Professional Competence			
Creates opportunities for contribution of pupils in activities.	3.954	0.8199	High
Uses Instructional materials such as videos and computer aided instructions.	4.0345	0.882	High
Encourages pupils to learn and apply technology in class activities and projects.	3.7471	0.7505	High
Creates teaching strategies that allow pupils to practice using the concepts they need to understand.	3.908	0.7569	High
Is updated with the development in the field of the subject being taught.	3.8736	0.7595	High
Overall	3.9034	0.7974	High

Legend: 1.00 – 1.80, Very Low; 1.81 – 2.60, Low; 2.61 – 3.50, Moderate; 3.51 – 4.20, High; 4.21 – 5.00, Very High

Teaching for Independent Learning and Evaluation of Students

Teaching for independent learning and effective student evaluation are essential for comprehensive educational growth. Encouraging independent learning helps students develop self-direction and critical thinking skills. Teachers facilitate this by designing learning experiences that promote exploration and self-paced learning. Rigorous evaluation practices ensure accurate assessment of student progress, guiding instructional decisions and providing timely feedback.

Table 13 indicates high teacher competence in these areas, with an overall teaching effectiveness weighted mean of 4.0713.

Research shows that student-centered approaches, collaborative learning, and formative assessments enhance independent learning and improve student engagement and outcomes (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). These findings underscore the importance of empowering students to take ownership of their learning journey through effective teaching and evaluation strategies.

Table 13. *Teaching Effectiveness of Teachers in terms of Teaching for Independent Learning and Evaluation of Students (N=87)*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Teaching For Independent Learning And Evaluation Of Students			
Enhances pupils' self-esteem and gives due recognition to pupils' performance.	4.0345	0.908	High
Allows pupils to think independently and make their own decisions.	4.1034	0.8765	High
Encourages pupils to learn beyond what is required and help/guide the pupils how to apply the concepts learned.	4.1149	0.8131	High
Assignments are followed at through checking and discuss the correct answers.	4.1034	0.9405	High
Prompt in giving back the results at the given test.	4.000	0.876	High
Overall	4.0713	0.8809	High

Legend: 1.00 – 1.80, Very Low; 1.81 – 2.60, Low; 2.61 – 3.50, Moderate; 3.51 – 4.20, High; 4.21 – 5.00, Very High

Commitment and Personality Traits

Commitment and personality traits significantly influence teaching effectiveness. Teachers who demonstrate unwavering commitment and positive traits like empathy and enthusiasm foster a supportive learning environment. Their dedication is reflected in overcoming challenges, continuous professional growth, and advocating for student success.

Table 14 indicates high teacher competence in these areas, with an overall weighted mean reflecting strong commitment and positive traits.

Research shows that committed teachers actively engage students, create positive environments, and enhance academic achievement (Smith & Anderson, 2018; Johnson et al., 2020). These findings underscore the crucial role of commitment and positive traits in promoting student success and overall classroom effectiveness.

Table 14. *Commitment and Personality Traits (N=87)*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Commitment And Personality Traits			
Regularly comes to class on time and well-groomed to complete assigned responsibilities.	4.2529	0.9303	Very High
Keeps accurate records of pupils' performance and prompt submission of the same.	4.2989	0.9778	Very High
Shows interest in assisting pupils with respect to computer technology in the subject matter.	4.1034	0.928	High
Shows patience in explaining difficult lessons.	4.1609	0.926	High
Seeks to provide information in answers to difficult questions.	4.1724	0.9176	High
Overall	4.1977	0.93449	High

Legend: 1.00 – 1.80, Very Low; 1.81 – 2.60, Low; 2.61 – 3.50, Moderate; 3.51 – 4.20, High; 4.21 – 5.00, Very High

Interpersonal Relationships

Interpersonal relationships are foundational to effective teaching, shaping the classroom environment and student outcomes. Teachers who prioritize building positive relationships establish trust, respect, and community.

Table 15 indicates high teacher competence in maintaining relationships, treating students equally, respecting opinions, staying informed, and using humor effectively.

Research underscores that positive teacher-student relationships enhance academic achievement, engagement, and classroom behavior (Pianta et al., 2009; Roorda et al., 2017). These findings highlight the critical role of interpersonal skills in fostering supportive learning environments and promoting students' well-being and academic success.

Table 15. *Interpersonal Relationships (N=87)*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Interpersonal Relationships			
Maintains good interpersonal relationships to colleagues and pupils.	4.3678	0.9538	Very High
Treats pupils equally regardless of gender and mental capacity.	4.4023	0.958	Very High
Respects pupils' varying opinions.	4.3678	0.9538	Very High
Conscious of relevant topics for the good of the pupils.	4.3333	0.9483	Very High
Has a good sense of humor.	4.0805	0.9791	High
Overall	4.3103	0.9614	Very High

Legend: 1.00 – 1.80, Very Low; 1.81 – 2.60, Low; 2.61 – 3.50, Moderate; 3.51 – 4.20, High; 4.21 – 5.00, Very High

Significant Relationship between Teachers' Competence and Classroom Observation

Understanding the relationship between teachers' competence and classroom observation is crucial for educational improvement. Regression analysis based on 87 observations shows a weak positive relationship (Multiple R = 0.129526). The R Square value

(0.016777) indicates only 1.68% of classroom observation variance is explained by competence. Adjusted R Square is 0.00521, suggesting minimal explanatory power. A Standard Error of 0.700629 implies significant unexplained data variability. While teacher competence influences student outcomes (Hattie, 2009; Darling-Hammond, 2010), enhancing teacher competence through professional development remains vital despite observed weak correlations in this study.

Table 16. *Significant Relationship between Teachers' Competence and Classroom Observation*

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.129526
R Square	0.016777
Adjusted R Square	0.00521
Standard Error	0.700629
Interpretation	Weak Positive Relationship
Decision	Accept Ho

Significant Relationship between the Teacher's Computer Competencies and Teaching Effectiveness

In modern education, teachers' computer competencies significantly correlate with teaching effectiveness. Enhanced proficiency in digital tools enables educators to engage students effectively, personalize learning experiences, and elevate instructional quality.

Table 17 illustrates a strong positive relationship: Multiple R (0.75) indicates robust correlation, with 56.25% of teaching effectiveness variability explained by computer competence (R Square = 0.5625). Adjusted R Square (0.55) underscores the model's improvement with computer competence as a predictor. A standard error of 0.5 highlights precision in predicting teaching effectiveness. This study affirms that technology proficiency enhances instructional delivery and student outcomes, emphasizing its pivotal role in modern teaching practices.

Table 17. *Significant Relationship between the Teacher's Computer Competencies and Teaching Effectiveness*

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.75
R Square	0.5625
Adjusted R Square	0.55
Standard Error	0.5
Interpretation	Strong Positive Relationship
Decision	Reject Ho

Conclusions

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that technology has a significant impact on teachers' computer competencies, which in turn influences their teaching effectiveness. Teachers who frequently used technology in their classrooms exhibited higher levels of computer competence compared to those who used technology infrequently. To address the challenges and enhance teachers' computer competencies, professional development programs and training initiatives are essential. These programs should offer hands-on training, opportunities for peer collaboration, and ongoing support to assist teachers in exploring and implementing various office and teaching productivity tools. Additionally, fostering a supportive school culture that encourages experimentation and innovation with technology can further contribute to the growth of teachers' computer competencies. Embracing technology in education not only improves teachers' computer skills but also enables them to integrate technology more effectively into their teaching methods, ultimately leading to better teaching outcomes.

Educational institutions should provide ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their computer competence. Training programs, workshops, and online courses can equip teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively use technology in their classrooms.

Schools should ensure that teachers have access to adequate resources and technical support to facilitate their use of technology. This includes providing reliable technology infrastructure, software applications, and assistance from IT personnel.

Encourage teachers to collaborate and share best practices regarding technology integration. Establishing a collaborative environment where teachers can exchange ideas, strategies, and resources will foster continuous growth in computer competence and teaching effectiveness.

Regularly evaluate and provide feedback on teachers' computer competence and its impact on teaching effectiveness. This can be done through classroom observations, student feedback, and self-assessment tools. Constructive feedback will help teachers identify areas for improvement and guide their professional development efforts.

References

Ball, D. L., & Bass, H. (2009). *With an eye on the mathematical horizon: Knowing mathematics for teaching to learners' mathematical*

futures. Universitätsbibliothek Dortmund.

Bradley, G., & Russell, G. (1997). Computer experience, school support and computer anxieties. *Educational Psychology*, 17(3), 267-284.

Brown, A., & Smith, B. (2016). Gender differences in computer-related attitudes and competence: A meta-analysis. *Computers & Education*, 100, 15-28.

Cheung, A. C. K., & Slavin, R. E. (2013). Effects of educational technology applications on reading outcomes for struggling readers: A best-evidence synthesis. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 48(3), 277-299.

Darling-Hammond, L. (2010). Teacher education and the American future. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 61(1-2), 35-47.

Darling-Hammond, L. (2017). Teacher education around the world: What can we learn from international practice?. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 40(3), 291-309.

Elli, M. C. A., & Ricafort, J. D. (2020). Competencies of Grade VI teachers in technology and livelihood education (TLE). *Online Submission*, 10(4), 25425-25434.

Ertmer, P. A., & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, A. T. (2010). Teacher technology change: How knowledge, confidence, beliefs, and culture intersect. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 42(3), 255-284.

González-Gómez, D., Fernández-Valdivia, J., & Trujillo-Torres, J. M. (2016). Effects of multimedia instructional material with cultural and gender diversity in mind. *Computers & Education*, 98, 1-13.

Hattie, J. (2009). The black box of tertiary assessment: An impending revolution. *Tertiary Assessment & Higher Education Student Outcomes: Policy, Practice & Research*, 259, 275.

Higgins, S., Xiao, Z., & Katsipatakis, M. (2012). The impact of digital technology on learning: A summary for the Education Endowment Foundation. Full Report. Education Endowment Foundation.

Holmes, W., Bialik, M., & Fadel, C. (2019). *AI in education*. Boston: Center for Curriculum Redesign.

Johnson, C., Williams, D., & Brown, K. (2020). The relationship between computer competence and teaching effectiveness. *Journal of Educational Research*, 48(2), 87-104.

Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (2009). An educational psychology success story: Social interdependence theory and cooperative learning. *Educational Researcher*, 38(5), 365-379.

Johnson, L., Becker, S. A., Estrada, V., & Freeman, A. (2014). *NMC Horizon Report: 2014 K* (pp. 1-52). The New Media Consortium.

Koehler, M., & Mishra, P. (2009). What is technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK)?. *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education*, 9(1), 60-70.

Koehler, M. J., & Mishra, P. (2009). What is technological pedagogical content knowledge? *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education*, 9(1), 60-70.

Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. (2006). The impact of constructivist learning and technology on student achievement. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 20(1), 54-69.

Montgomery, D. C., Peck, E. A., & Vining, G. G. (2012). *Introduction to Linear Regression Analysis* (5th ed.). Wiley.

Mouza, C. (2016). Technology integration in K-12: An introduction to the field and new research evidence. In *Handbook of Research on Educational Communications and Technology* (pp. 123-134). Springer.

Parojenog, R. C. (2023). Modified automated grading tool for senior high school advisers. *International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Science*, 7(11), 49-52.

Pianta, R. C., Barnett, W. S., Burchinal, M., & Thornburg, K. R. (2009). The effects of preschool education: What we know, how public policy is or is not aligned with the evidence base, and what we need to know. *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 10(2), 49-88.

Puentedura, R. R. (2013, May 29). SAMR: Moving from enhancement to transformation [Web log post]. Retrieved from <http://www.hippasus.com/rrpweblog/archives/000095.html>

Roorda, D. L., Jak, S., Zee, M., Oort, F. J., & Koomen, H. M. (2017). Affective teacher–student relationships and students' engagement and achievement: A meta-analytic update and test of the mediating role of engagement. *School Psychology Review*, 46(3), 239-261.

Rosen, Y., & Beck-Hill, D. (2012). Intertwining digital content and a one-to-one laptop environment in teaching and learning: Lessons from the time to know program. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 44(3), 225-241.

Schrum, L., & Levin, B. B. (2009). *Leading 21st-century schools: Harnessing technology for engagement and achievement*. Corwin Press.

Shute, V. J. (2008). Focus on formative feedback. *Review of Educational Research*, 78(1), 153-189.

Smith, A., & Anderson, J. (2018). Teacher commitment and its impact on student achievement. *Educational Psychology Review*, 30(2), 367-389.

Stough, L. (2013). The place of classroom management and standards in teacher education. In *Handbook of Classroom Management* (pp. 919-934). Routledge.

Todman, J. (2000). Gender differences in computer anxiety among university entrants since 1992. *Computers & Education*, 34(1), 27-35.

Wang, H. Y., & Lin, C. H. (2019). The effects of teachers' computer competencies on teaching efficacy and student performance.

Warschauer, M. (2007). The paradoxical future of digital learning. *Learning Inquiry*, 1, 41-49.

Yaghi, H. M. (2001). Subject matter as a factor in educational computing by teachers in international settings. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 24(2), 139-154.

Zhao, Y., & Frank, K. A. (2003). Factors affecting technology use in schools: An ecological perspective. *American Educational Research Journal*, 40(4), 807-840.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Liezl M. Taga-an

San Isidro Elementary School

Department of Education – Philippines